

PEIDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF MULTICULTURALISM IN AZERBAIJANI EDUCATION

Quliyeva C.

Baku State University, master student of the Faculty of International Relations and Economics
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Abstract

The purpose of the study - Programs and textbooks, teaching and methodological aids, recommendations, etc. for the effective organization of the teaching of languages of minorities and ethnic groups. preparation and publication are in constant focus.

The methodology of the research - Multiculturalism means "many cultures" in English. Azerbaijan has been known for centuries as a place where different civilizations meet, where the environment of national and cultural diversity is formed, where people of different nations and religions live in peace, tranquility, mutual understanding and dialogue. Multiculturalism and tolerance have historically been a way of life for Azerbaijanis, and today they have become a way of life for every citizen of the Azerbaijani state, regardless of their national identity, language or religion. The rich multicultural past of the Azerbaijani people lives not only in the tolerant way of life of our people today, but also in the literary-artistic, scientific-philosophical, political-legal sources and documents created by them.

The practical importance of the research In modern times, it is important to study the real situation in order to manage the quality of education, monitor and forecast the dynamics of development. In this case, assessment is considered an important pedagogical tool. Assessment creates objective conditions to improve the educational process, to increase the effectiveness of the learning process, to determine what students have mastered, what skills they have and what qualitative changes have taken place in them. The activities carried out in this direction in our country are aimed at preserving, developing and harmonizing the cultural diversity of representatives of different religions and nations around the world.

The results of the research -. Undoubtedly, Azerbaijan, as a country that has been contributing to the development of multicultural values for more than a century, will spare no effort to maintain peace, stability and sustainable development, not only in the South Caucasus but in the world as a whole.

Originality and scientific novelty of the research - Today, there are new realities in the culture of Azerbaijan, in the education system of Azerbaijan. The post-war period is especially important for the restoration of socio-political, cultural, educational and economic ties in the region, and this process today requires a more multicultural approach.

Keywords: multikulturalism, education, multikultural education

Introduction

Azerbaijan, which has unique national and highly humane traditions, is one of the rare countries that spread the multiculturalism education principles around the world. The established relations in this area in our country confirm that multiculturalism is the national quality of our people formed throughout history and has always been the way of life of society. Today, the reality is that the Azerbaijani model of multiculturalism has already been formed, which, as a perfect example, creates a full basis for the peaceful life and equal activity of many different ethnic groups in our country.

The order of President Ilham Aliyev "on declaring 2016 the Year of multiculturalism in the Republic of Azerbaijan" dated January 11, 2016 also shows that preservation, development and wide propaganda of the traditions of multiculturalism are always in the focus of attention of the country's leadership. For this purpose, over the years, numerous events of international and local importance have been held and are being held now and it is planned to hold such events again.

Employees of the Ministry of Education, Baku City Education Department, representatives of Baku International multiculturalism Center, "Great Silk Way" International Youth Union, Azerbaijan Young

Lawyers' Union, teachers and students participate in the events. The main purpose of the trainings is to inform schoolchildren and students about tolerance and multiculturalism in Azerbaijan, to show the importance of Peaceful living of all nations, ethnic groups regardless of their ethnic, religious, racial and cultural background.

"We are all human and we are all the same", "my multicultural Azerbaijan", etc. the presentations were made by trainers and young leaders who presented their groups.

Formation of multicultural education

The changes taking place in the globalizing world encourage us to make changes in all areas and take the right steps for a successful future. One of these areas and the first is the education sector. Education is the most effective tool to touch people's lives. The successful future is in the hands of tolerant respected persons who are able to listen to each other to the end, respect each other's spiritual and cultural values.

Multicultural education is an educational strategy designed to help students, students, respond to many problems caused by rapidly changing demographics and help teachers. Students are informed about the his-

tory, culture and activities of various groups, associations, with them it is concluded that the future society is pluralistic.

Multicultural education is connected with education and instruction designed to teach different races, religions, cultures of peoples in the education system. This approach focused on teaching and learning is based on the development of cultural pluralism in racist societies.

Multicultural education is based on the principle of a single justice for all cultures, regardless of all cultures, and seeks to remove obstacles on the way to success for students from different cultural differences. In practice, educators may modify or remove educational policies, programs, materials, classes and guidelines that discriminate against different cultural differences or are not fair enough. [2].

Against the backdrop of rapidly changing, interchangeable realities in the world, we sometimes face unexpected events and facts, we face new ones without ending the analysis of the realities. But in any case, there is a reality that has no alternative to the new world order, without taking it into account, it seems impossible to direct the processes to the desired direction. This is the ideology of multiculturalism and the need to embody it in society. Without taking into account this simple fact, it is difficult to achieve mutual agreement and fair balance in the world.

Being a democratic, secular and legal state, Azerbaijan strives to live in peace and cooperation with all countries of the world. Our people highly appreciated the tranquility since ancient times, established good relations with their neighbors, rejoiced at their successes and shared their troubles. Tolerance, respect for Culture, Education, Customs and traditions of other nations have become an integral part of Azerbaijani ideology for thousands of years. Azerbaijanis respected the peoples living both inside and outside the country. It is no coincidence that religious tolerance, traditions of multiculturalism occupy an important place in the modern Azerbaijani society and its moral values.

Continuing decently the political activity of national leader Heydar Aliyev in the field of protection and development of multicultural values in the country, President Ilham Aliyev meets with the representatives of the nations and religious communities living in our country, is interested in their needs and problems, and congratulates them on national and religious holidays. The establishment of the state consultation on international, multicultural and religious affairs of the Republic of Azerbaijan on 2014 February 28 by the order of the president is also an indicator of the successful policy of multiculturalism. At the same time, as a result of considering multiculturalism as one of the main components of the state policy, the Baku International multiculturalism center was established in May 2014 by the decree of President Ilham Aliyev.

Azerbaijan is already perceived in the world as a space of multiculturalism and dialogue among civilizations. We should emphasize the great work of the Heydar Aliyev Foundation in presenting the multicultural values of our people to the world. Issues of multiculturalism and tolerance occupy a key place in the activities

of the Heydar Aliyev Foundation, but they also cross Azerbaijan and cover a large geographical area from Vatican to Asia, from East to Africa. The Heydar Aliyev Foundation contributes to the establishment of human values such as humanism, solidarity and tolerance among different peoples, as well as the perfect tradition formed in our country.

It is known that education is of great importance in spreading the ideas of multiculturalism. Today, great attention is paid to the teaching of the basics of multiculturalism in Azerbaijan's higher education. And this is natural, because it is important to study multiculturalism, which has become a state policy, by young people who are the founders of the future. Multiculturalism is not a campaign event, carried out within a certain year. Multiculturalism is an important component of the Azerbaijani model of social, cultural and social progress, its base element. This model clearly shows on the example of the Republic of Azerbaijan what needs to be done to develop mutual trust between countries and peoples, attracting the attention of the whole world. The upbringing of young people, which are already the driving force of our society today, in this spirit guarantees the successful development of the state policy in the future.

Today, the basics of multiculturalism are taught at the higher schools of our republic (mainly master's degree). This subject of a socio-humanitarian nature helps to increase students' outlook, regardless of their professional orientation. Special importance is given to teaching of the subject "model of multiculturalism in Azerbaijan" in educational institutions.

Today, magazines, Almanac, textbooks and monographs devoted to intercultural communication are published in many countries of the world, including Azerbaijan, and purposeful work is carried out to ensure the training of education and culture workers in this field. Education in particular acts as an important tool in social adaptation and integration with its various forms and degrees. It has become an important factor in ensuring national security and regional stability [3]. Education is able to eliminate stereotypes and boundaries between ethnic groups, including inequality and injustice.

It should be noted that, starting from the fall semester of 2014-2015 academic year, the subject of "Azerbaijan multiculturalism" has been taught in well-known universities of Italy, Russia, Bulgaria, Belarus, Lithuania, Czech Republic, Georgia and other countries, as well as in the country's higher education institutions. The summer and winter schools realized on the special initiative of Kamal Abdullayev, chairman of the Board of patronage of the Baku International multiculturalism centre (Baku International multiculturalism centre) and state advisor on International, multiculturalism and religious issues, aim to complete the basic theoretical knowledge gained by students and teachers of foreign universities about Azerbaijan during the semester by seeing our country clearly. From the first semester of the 2015 academic year, the subjects "introduction to multiculturalism" (Bachelor's degree) and "Azerbaijani multiculturalism" (master's degree) are taught in 29 higher schools of Azerbaijan, as well as in

11 higher schools of the world. The ongoing measures taken to form and develop a space based on a highly developed cultural environment in our country have reached an even higher level today under the leadership of President Ilham Aliyev.

Azerbaijan is a multinational country, a place where different nations and peoples live and operate in an atmosphere of mutual understanding. The independent Azerbaijan state and its founder Heydar Aliyev paid attention to language, education, culture, customs and traditions of the ethnic minorities living in our country. The Republic of Azerbaijan, which is a full member of the Council of Europe, has always kept the principles of "European Charter of Regional languages or languages of small Peoples" adopted by this organization on November 5, 1992, and has taken practical measures for their implementation.

Great leader Heydar Aliyev paid attention to the preparation and promotion of the idea of azerbaijanism and created conditions for the rapid development of tolerance and multiculturalism in Azerbaijan. At the present stage, the ideology of azerbaijanism is successfully continued by President Ilham Aliyev, a worthy political successor of the Great Leader. The citizens of Azerbaijan belonging to different peoples and religions demonstrated solidarity in the 44-day Patriotic War and demonstrated our unity to the world by winning a brilliant victory over the enemy.

Political and at the same time true successor of Heydar Aliyev, President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev new content education concept of his predecessor - the ideology of azerbaijanism has been developed from the scientific-theoretical and practical-applied philosophy of multiculturalism, the philosophy of intercultural dialogue, the obvious result of which is that our country gained fame as the most advanced Cultural, at the same time tolerant country in the world.

We can confidently say that the event of multiculturalism, intercultural dialogue and tolerance caused by Heydar Aliyev's ideology of azerbaijanism was the main priority area in the public administration policy of Mr. Ilham Aliyev, the program Project - the philosophy of life of society is comprehended in its essence, and this ideology has become the concept of equal coexistence in the Republic of Azerbaijan, which attaches serious importance to secular and universal values, inter-ethnic dialogue in the last 20 years.

Today, Azerbaijan is already one of the world's recognized centers of multiculturalism. In the context of sociocultural development patterns of XXI century Ilham Aliyev understanding and re-evaluating the multicultural traditions of our people as an integral part of spiritual culture is of particular importance. International economic and cultural relations are steadily expanding. The process of exchange of values has intensified. The world is on the verge of a new civilization. The priority and strategic goal of transformation of human history into this innovative stage is to bring together a single sociocultural space, primarily through the integration of different cultures and worldviews.

Whether this goal is achieved or not significantly depends on revealing universal values, providing a common approach to them by carriers of different religions and cultures, and joint activities aimed at solving many complex humanitarian, social, cultural, moral and economic problems. Continuous development requires that people, in a big sense, people voluntarily and consciously cooperate and achieve a goal. This can become a reality only thanks to the analysis of intercultural relations, the development of joint stable mechanisms for solving problems, in a word, the successful implementation of the multicultural strategy of human development. Located for centuries in the "crossroads" of the two worlds-Europe and Asia not only geographically, but also culturally, Azerbaijan is also pursuing a political course based on these realities. The successes of our country, which has always played an important role in the intercultural dialogue, are more remarkable now. Of course, predicting the future with all its accuracy is a very complex task. But there is no doubt that in the context of the realities of Azerbaijan, intercultural dialogue has great prospects and our country is capable of becoming an indispensable participant in this process. To do this, the Azerbaijani state has all the possibilities: material and human resources, the National Spirit, Education and traditions. Today, under the leadership of President Ilham Aliyev, grandiose works are underway to implement the ideas of multiculturalism in Azerbaijan at a very high level. In the light of this work, the foundation of which was laid by national leader Heydar Aliyev is modern, tolerant, a single Azerbaijan with a multicultural education system, a highly established monolithic Azerbaijani nation is being formed.

Conclusion

The formation of national-moral consciousness in the modern period, the acquisition of the personality of moral and moral qualities - these include such qualities as tolerance, tolerance, high-level development of education, respect for others, empathy. All these are considered important factors in the development of society. That is why the problem of national-moral, moral education of a person and the upbringing of a decent person is always in the spotlight of the state.

The state strategy for the development of education in the Republic of Azerbaijan "realizing responsibility, respecting the principles of democracy and national traditions of its people, human rights and freedoms, adhering to the ideas of azerbaijanism, raising independent and creative thinking citizen and personality; protecting and developing national moral and universal values, having wide outlook... training of personnel" is one of the main tasks of the education system [4]. As we have already mentioned, the main responsibility lies with teachers. Because along with the preservation of multicultural values, it is very important to bring them to future generations, to study and to bring them into essence. Therefore, instilling the realities of Azerbaijan to young people in any field, promotion of the rich multicultural past, education and the steps taken by the state to protect cultural diversity are the guarantee of the multicultural future.